

Studies on Benzothiazolohemicyanine Dyes : Synthesis, Structural Correlation with UV-Absorption Maxima

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Novel applications of some polyenic cyanines and infrared dyes especially in optical information storage devices, solar energy conversion systems, histological staining, antimicrobial operations and also as tools for lasers have been described¹. The hemicyanines have been subject of several investigations and some data have been reported on the effect of substituents in the main chromophoric chain and on the effect of elongation of the chain, based on optical absorption data and on photosensitisation properties²⁻⁶.

In this present investigation two substituted benzophenone derivatives, namely, 4-dimethylamino-4'-methoxybenzophenone and 4-dimethylamino-4'-nitrobenzophenone were synthesised and condensed with 2-methylbenzothiazolium methiodide and 2-methyl-6-substituted-benzothiazole methiodides using piperidine as basic catalyst and ethanolic DMF as solvent, thus affording a series of benzothiazolohemicyanine dyes (BHD).

Results and Discussion

A study of the absorption maxima of the twenty one

new benzothiazolohemicyanine dyes (Table 1) with those of the reported butadienylene chain hemicyanines^{5,6} and quinaldine hemicyanines⁴ leads to some interesting generalisations. The chain β -phenyl substituents uniformly result bathochromic shifts in absorption maxima relative to their corresponding β -phenyl unsubstituted analogues, irrespective of the nature of the groups attached to the β -phenyl ring, i.e. whether they are electron-attracting, such as NO₂, or electron-donating, such as MeO. Furthermore, nitro group absorbs at longer wavelength than the methoxy group. When these dyes are compared with the reported butadienylene chain hemicyanines^{5,6} or quinaldine chain hemicyanines⁴ they show hypsochromic shifts. The hypsochromism with butadienylene chain hemicyanines may be due to chain elongation, but hypsochromism when compared to quinaldine hemicyanines with same conjugation is remarkable. Perhaps it is due to the ring strain of thiazole nucleus in comparison with the pyridine nucleus.

The increase of absorption maxima in the dyes having 4'-additives in β -phenyl nucleus (electron-accepting or electron-donating) than unsubstituted ring needs attention. Substitution is supposed to perturb the benzene ring both by inductive and resonance effects⁷⁻⁹. A substituent with electron-releasing inductive effect lowers the ionisation energy of the substituted benzene, while one with electron-withdrawing inductive effect increases it. The resonance effect lowers the ionisation energy of the molecule. The increasing or decreasing or progressive variation in ionisation energy results in bathochromic shift which corroborate the reported data⁷. The functional group at the 6-position of the benzothiazole ring shows consistent bathochromic shift in comparison to unsubstituted one in the order : I > Br > Cl > Me > H, OEt > OMe. The bathochromic shifts to halogen derivatives are in conformity with the earlier observations⁶. It is presumably due to electron contribution and polarisation ability of the halogen species. The 6-additives cause increase in absorption due to progressive weighting.

Experimental

2-Methylbenzothiazole and 2-methyl-6-substituted-benzothiazoles were synthesised by following the reported

NOTE

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF BTHC DYES*

Dye	Name ^a	Yield %	M.p. °C	Crystal ^b shape and colour	λ_{\max} nm	ν_{\max} cm ⁻¹
Series I :						
¹ D ₁	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)SBzThMeI	42	161	bgp	349, 309	2950–3040 (C–H) aromatic
¹ D ₂	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-ClBzThMeI	47	172	dbc	351, 312	1 590–1 640 (C=C) aromatic under
¹ D ₃	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-BrBzThMeI	63	184	dbc	354, 312	conjugation with C=N
¹ D ₄	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-IBzThMeI	46	210	dl	356, 313	5 50–740 (C–X)
¹ D ₅	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-MeBzThMeI	58	164	rbl	350, 311	2420–2450 quaternary nitrogen and sulphur atom
¹ D ₆	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-OMeBzThMeI	55	192	dgc	352, 311	
¹ D ₇	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β - <i>p</i>)S-6-OEtBzThMeI	53	210	bl	353	
Series II :						
² D ₁	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)SBzThMeI	51	182	bgl	362, 350	3000–3090 (C–H) aromatic
² D ₂	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-ClBzThMeI	50	202	rbl	369, 352	1640–1690 (C=C) aromatic under
² D ₃	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-BrBzThMeI	48	208	oc	370, 352	conjugation with C=N 570–790 (C–X)
² D ₄	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-IBzThMeI	56	238	bl	372, 358	2430–2470 may be due to quaternary nitrogen and sulphur atoms
² D ₅	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-MeBzThMeI	48	209	l'bl	368, 340	
² D ₆	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-OMeBzThMeI	56	201	fg'l	369, 342	
² D ₇	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Np)S-6-OEtBzThMeI	52	207	bgc	370, 345	
Series III :						
³ D ₁	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)SBzThMeI	49	181	bc	356, 318	3010–3050 (C–H) aromatic
³ D ₂	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-ClBzThMeI	41	209	bp	361, 342	1640–1680 (C=C) aromatic under
³ D ₃	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-BrBzThMeI	54	203	dvp	363, 343	conjugation with C=N
³ D ₄	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-IBzThMeI	55	210	dbc	365, 346	1050–1080 (C–O) alkoxy
³ D ₅	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-MrBzThMeI	43	206	c''c'c	359, 335	570–800 (C–X) 2420–2460 may be due to quaternary nitrogen and sulphur atoms
³ D ₆	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-MeOBzThMeI	48	208	dbc	360, 340	
³ D ₇	2- <i>p</i> -DMAP(β -4'-Mp)S-6-EtOBzThMeI	51	218	tc'c	362, 343	

*All compounds gave satisfactory N and halogen analyses.

^a*p*-DMAP = *p*-dimethylaminophenyl; (β -*p*) = β -phenyl; S = styryl; BzThMeI = benzothiazole methiodide; Np = nitrophenyl; Mp = methoxyphenyl.

^bb = brown; bg = bottle green; c = crystals; c' = coloured; c'' = chocolate; d = dark; g = green; l = leaflets; o = orange; p = platelets; t = tea; v = violet.

methods^{9,10} with some procedural alterations as suggested by Banerji *et al.*³. Quaternisation was carried out by adopting the method of Johnson and Adams¹¹ with some modifications⁵. The auxochromic benzophenones were prepared following the reported method¹² with some slight modifications.

Benzothiazolohemicyanine dyes: Condensations to form the dyes were affected by previously reported general method with some procedural modifications. A mixture of equimolar proportions of the complex auxochromic ketones and quaternised bases dissolved in ethanolic DMF (20 ml) in presence of piperidine (4 drops) as basic catalyst was refluxed for 6–8 h under anhydrous condition. The resulting solution was concentrated, cooled and left overnight at ambient temperature. The recovered crude dyes were crystallised from methanol.

Electronic spectra were recorded on a Shimadzu UV-160 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Fourier Transform spectrophotometer.

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